

ON A NONLOCAL IN TIME INITIAL-BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEM

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partment of Mathematical Physics Equations***Abstract**

The present work is devoted to finding a solution to a mixed problem for the heat equation with nonlocal conditions in time in a rectangle. The solution is sought in the class of continuous functions. A theorem is presented providing the justification of the classical solution obtained.

Keywords: mixed problem, condition of orthogonality, non-local conditions, Fourier series, basis.

In practical heat transfer processes, it is sometimes required that, at certain moments in time, the temperatures at specific points of a heated body attain (or closely approximate) prescribed values. Problems of this type arise, for instance, in the design of household appliances, in the development of aerospace structures, in agriculture and etc. From a mathematical perspective, such problems are formulated as boundary value problems for the heat equation with additional conditions specified at different time instances. In general, these problems are ill-posed, since it is well known that the present thermal state does not determine the past thermal history with sufficient accuracy; that is, heat conduction problems with reversed time are ill-posed [1]–[4]. Nevertheless, it turns out that in most cases the ill-posedness is primarily associated with instability, while exact present data correspond to certain exact past states. Consequently, the problem under consideration can be reformulated as a boundary value problem for the heat equation with nonlocal boundary conditions [5]–[7].

Thus, we consider the equation

$$u_t = a^2 u_{xx}, 0 < x < 1, 0 < t < T \quad (1)$$

under boundary conditions

$$u(t, 0) = u(t, 1) = 0 \quad (2)$$

and initial condition

$$\alpha u(0, x) + \beta u(T, x) = \Phi(x), \quad (3)$$

where α, β are real constants, $|\alpha| + |\beta| \neq 0, \Phi(x) \in L_2(0, 1)$.

Condition (3) represents a nonlocal condition that inherently includes the initial condition.

Therefore, we begin by solving this problem.

Let us specify that a solution to problem (1)–(3) is understood as a function $u(t, x)$ satisfying the following conditions:

- 1) $u(t, x) \in C^{1,2}(0 < t \leq T, 0 \leq x \leq 1) \cap L_2(0 \leq t \leq T, 0 \leq x \leq 1)$;
- 2) $u(t, x)$ satisfies equation (1) and boundary condition (2) in the classical sense;
- 3) $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \int_0^1 |\alpha u(t, x) + \beta u(T, x) - \Phi(x)|^2 dx = 0$.

By expressing the solution of problem (1)–(3) in terms of a Fourier series with respect to the basis $\{\sqrt{2} \sin k\pi x\}$, we obtain:

$$u(t, x) = \sqrt{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} u_k(t) \sin k\pi x \quad (4)$$

Substituting this expression into (1) and (3), and taking into account the expansion (4), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [u'_k(t) + a^2 k^2 \pi^2 u_k(t)] \sin k\pi x &= 0, \\ \sqrt{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [\alpha u_k(0) + \beta u_k(T) - \Phi_k] \sin k\pi x &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

From these equations, taking into account the orthonormality of the system $\{\sqrt{2} \sin k\pi x\}$, it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} u'_k(t) + a^2 k^2 \pi^2 u_k(t) &= 0 \\ \alpha u_k(0) + \beta u_k(T) &= \Phi_k. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} u_k(t) &= C_k e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t}, \\ C_k [\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T}] &= \Phi_k. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, if

$$\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T} \neq 0$$

for all natural numbers k , then

$$u_k(t) = \frac{\Phi_k}{\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T}} \cdot e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t}$$

and therefore a formal representation of the solution to problem (1)–(3) is obtained:

$$u(t, x; \Phi) = 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Phi_k e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t}}{\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T}} \cdot \sin k\pi x. \quad (5)$$

Assume that the following condition is fulfilled:

1⁰. Let either либо α/β , or $\alpha/\beta < -e^{-a^2 \pi^2 T}$.

The following theorem holds:

Theorem. Suppose that condition 1⁰ is satisfied and $\Phi(x) \in L_2(0,1)$. Then the function $u(t, x, \Phi)$, defined by formula (5), is a solution of problem (1)–(3).

Proof. Note that from condition 1⁰ it follows that

$\alpha \neq 0, \beta \neq 0$ and

$$\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T} = \beta \frac{\alpha}{\beta} + e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T}$$

Therefore, if $\alpha/\beta < e^{-a^2 \pi^2 T}$, then we have

$$\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T} \geq \beta \left| \frac{\alpha}{\beta} \right| = \alpha,$$

and if $\alpha/\beta < -e^{-a^2 \pi^2 T}$, then

$$|\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T}| \geq |\beta| \left| \frac{\alpha}{\beta} + e^{-a^2 \pi^2 T} \right|$$

for all natural numbers k . Then, If we denote

$$C_0 = \min \left(\alpha + \frac{\alpha}{\beta} + e^{-a^2 \pi^2 T} \right)$$

It is clear that $c_0 > 0$, and

$$|\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T}| \geq C_0$$

for all natural numbers k .

Consequently, the following estimates hold:

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{\Phi_k e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t}}{\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T}} \cdot \sin k\pi x \right| &\leq C e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t}, \\ \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\Phi_k e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t}}{\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T}} \sin k\pi x \right| &\leq C k^2 e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t}, \\ \left| \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \frac{\Phi_k e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t}}{\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T}} \sin k\pi x \right| &\leq C k^2 e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

This estimates show that series (5), as well as the series obtained from it by formal differentiation once with respect to t , or twice with respect to x converge uniformly on any compact set $[t_0, T] \times [0,1]$, where $t_0 > 0$.

Then for function $u(t, x, \Phi)$, defined by formula (5), we have:

$$u(t, x, \Phi) \in C^{1,2}(0 < t \leq T, 0 \leq x \leq 1) \quad (7)$$

Moreover, from (5), using the orthonormality of the basis $\{\sqrt{2} \sin k\pi x\}$, we obtain:

$$\|u(t, x, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0 \leq t \leq T, 0 \leq x \leq 1)}^2 = \int_0^T \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Phi_k^2 e^{-2a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t}}{(\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T})^2} dt$$

and, in view of estimate (6), we conclude

$$\begin{aligned} \|u(t, x, \varphi)\|_{L_2(0 \leq t \leq T, 0 \leq x \leq 1)}^2 &\leq \frac{1}{C_0^2} \int_0^T \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \Phi_k^2 dt = \\ &= \frac{T}{C_0^2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \Phi_k^2 = \frac{T}{C_0^2} \|\Phi(x)\|_{L_2(0,1)}^2. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

It follows from (7) and (8) that condition 1) of the definition of a solution is satisfied. Moreover, due to the uniform convergence of series (5) and the series obtained from it by differentiating once with respect to t or twice with respect to x on any compact set $[t_0, T] \times [0,1]$, the operations $\frac{\partial}{\partial t}, \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}$, as well as the limits $x \rightarrow +0$ and $x \rightarrow 1 - 0$, can be passed under the summation sign in series (5).

Using this fact, a direct verification shows that $u(t, x, \Phi)$ satisfies equation (1) and the boundary conditions (2), i.e., condition 2) in the definition of a solution is also satisfied.

Next, note that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \int_0^1 |u(t, x, \Phi) + \beta u(t, x, \Phi) - \Phi(x)|^2 dx =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \int_0^1 \left| \sqrt{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{\Phi_k}{\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T}} (\alpha e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t} + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T}) - \varphi_k \right] \sin k\pi x \right|^2 dx = \\
&= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Phi_k^2 \alpha^2 (e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t} - 1)^2}{(\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T})^2}.
\end{aligned}$$

By virtue of estimate (6), the functional series on the right-hand side of the last formula is majorized by a convergent numerical series

$$\frac{\alpha^2}{c_0^2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \Phi_k^2 = \frac{\alpha^2}{c_0^2} \|\Phi(x)\|_{L_2(0,1)}^2.$$

Thus, this series converges uniformly for $t \in [0, T]$, and therefore the operation $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0}$ can be transferred under the sign of the sum:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Phi_k^2 \alpha^2 (e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t} - 1)^2}{(\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T})^2} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Phi_k^2 \alpha^2 (e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 t} - 1)^2}{(\alpha + \beta e^{-a^2 k^2 \pi^2 T})^2} = 0.$$

Thus, the following equality holds:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \int_0^1 |\alpha u(t, x, \Phi) + \beta u(t, x, \Phi) - \Phi(x)|^2 dx = 0$$

That is, condition 3) of the definition of a solution is also satisfied.

The theorem is proved.

References

1. В.П.Михайлов. Дифференциальные уравнения в частных производных// М. «Наука», 1976.
2. С.К.Годунов. Уравнения математической физики// М., 2-ое издание, исправленное и дополненное, «Наука», 1979, 392 с.
- 3.М.М.Лаврентьев. О некоторых некорректных задачах математической физики// Изд-во СО АН СССР, 1962.
- 4.Р.Латтес, Ж.- Л. Лионс. Метод квазиобращения и его приложения// М., «Мир», 1970, 336 с.
- 5.Ahmadov S.Z., Abbasova A.Kh. Solution of one mixed problem for the fourth order partial differential equation by sense of Shilov// International periodic scientific journal "Scientific Look into the Future", Ukraine, Odessa, Issue №19, Part I, November 2020, pp.103-107.
6. Ахмедов С.З., Касумов Р.А., Аббасова А.Х. Нахождение решения одной смешанной задачи для дифференциального уравнения четвертого порядка с производными в граничных условиях// Вестник Дагестанского государственного университета. Серия 1. Естественные науки. Республика Дагестан, г. Махачкала, 2023. Том 38. Вып. 2, стр. 90-99.
7. Ahmedov S.Z., Gasimov R.A., Habibov V.M. Solution of the mixed problem for the non-homogeneous parabolic equation with time derivative in the boundary conditions// Advanced mathematical modules and applications, Vol. 10, №1,2025, pp.184-193.